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Effects of Dietary Starch and Fatty Acid Supplementation on Milk Production and Metabolic Responses During the Immediate Postpartum in Dairy Cows

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INTERPRETIVE SUMMARY

Effects of dietary starch and fatty acid supplementation on milk production and metabolic responses during the immediate postpartum in dairy cows. *By Parales-Girón et al., page XXX.* This study tested how different levels of dietary starch and added fatty acids affect milk production in early-lactation Holstein cows. Cows fed more starch without extra fatty acids produced more milk and lactose, while fatty acid supplementation increased milk fat but reduced feed intake. The combination of high starch and added fatty acids resulted in intermediate responses, moderating each nutrient's individual effect. Overall, higher starch increased milk yield, and fatty acids improved milk fat content. The benefits of each depended on the other, and results from early feeding carried over to when a common diet was fed. Adjusting these nutrients helps improve dairy cow performance in early lactation.

Supplemental Table S1. Health events during the experiment within treatment diet¹.

Item	Treatment ²			
	LS	HS	LS+FA	HS+FA
During FR				
Ketosis	1	1	—	—
Retained placenta*	—	—	—	1
Milk fever	1	1	—	2
Mastitis	—	1	—	—
Digestive issues	—	1	—	—
During CO				
Mastitis	—	—	—	1

¹Retained placenta was defined as a failure to expel fetal membranes within 24 h after calving. Metritis was defined as the presence of fetid, watery, red-brown uterine discharge, and body temperature greater than 39.5°C. Clinical ketosis was recognized by clinical symptoms as anorexia and reduced milk production, accompanied by ketone bodies concentrations above 10 mg/dL in urine (Ketostix Reagent Strips, Bayer). Milk fever was recognized by showing muscle weakness, nervousness, muscle shaking, cold ears, and inability to rise.

²LS (diet containing starch at 22% DM and no supplemental FA); HS (diet containing starch at 28% DM and no supplemental FA); LS+FA (diet containing starch at 22% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1); HS+FA (diet containing starch at 28% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1).

*Retained placenta and metritis events were classified as clinical and were treated according to the farm protocols.

Supplemental Table S2. Dietary protein supply predictions from CNCPS¹ (v. 6.5.5) model

Item	Treatment ²			
	LS	HS	LS+FA	HS+FA
RUP, %CP	39.0	38.4	39.5	38.8
RDP, %CP	61.0	61.6	60.5	61.2
Metabolizable protein, g/d	2275	2237	2372	2320
Microbial metabolizable protein, %MP	47.7	49.6	46.5	48.6
Predicted supply of lysine, g/d	155	152	161	157
Lysine:Metabolizable Energy	3.06	2.95	2.94	2.83
Predicted supply of methionine, g/d	57.0	56.7	59.2	58.7
Methionine:Metabolizable Energy	1.13	1.10	1.08	1.06
<u>Lysine:Methionine</u>	<u>2.72</u>	<u>2.68</u>	<u>2.71</u>	<u>2.67</u>

¹Estimated predictions based on AMTS software (AMTS.Cattle.Professional v. 4.17.0.0; AMTS LLC; Van Amburgh et al., 2015) using data from Table 1 and Table 2 in the current study to reflect dietary protein supply of the experimental diets.

²LS (diet containing starch at 22% DM and no supplemental FA); HS (diet containing starch at 28% DM and no supplemental FA); LS+FA (diet containing starch at 22% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1); HS+FA (diet containing starch at 28% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1).

Supplemental Table S3. Milk production, BW, BCS, and plasma variables for cows fed treatment diets during the FR (d 1-23 postpartum).

Variable	Week	Treatment ¹				SEM	<i>P</i> -value ²							
		LS	HS	LS+FA	HS+FA		Starch	FA	Starch x FA	Time	Starch x Time	FA x Time	Starch x FA x Time	
DMI, kg/d	1	19.5	20.9	19.6	19.7	0.70								
	2	21.7 ^a	22.3 ^a	20.0 ^b	21.4 ^{ab}	0.70	0.10	0.05	0.83	<0.01	0.90	0.25	0.05	
	3	23.2 ^{ab}	24.2 ^a	21.9 ^b	22.6 ^{ab}	0.70								
Milk Yield, kg/d	1	38.8	42.4	39.4	38.1	1.36								
	2	43.2	47.9	42.9	44.3	1.36	0.05	0.11	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.78	0.44	
	3	47.5	52.0	47.8	48.5	1.36								
Milk Fat Yield, kg/d	1	1.87	2.05	2.09	1.96	0.08								
	2	1.96	2.12	2.10	2.11	0.08	0.36	0.26	0.06	<0.01	0.59	1.00	0.30	
	3	2.03	2.18	2.19	2.15	0.08								
Milk Fat Content, %	1	5.01	4.68	5.23	5.09	0.12								
	2	4.47	4.30	4.85	4.66	0.11	0.25	<0.01	0.87	<0.01	0.48	0.13	0.73	
	3	4.23	4.07	4.42	4.38	0.12								
Milk Protein Yield, kg/d	1	1.45	1.56	1.49	1.44	0.05								
	2	1.49	1.58	1.46	1.48	0.05	0.45	0.11	0.15	0.67	0.30	0.58	0.23	
	3	1.51	1.58	1.49	1.44	0.05								
Milk Protein Content, %	1	3.86	3.66	3.82	3.79	0.07								
	2	3.37	3.23	3.28	3.25	0.07	0.06	0.66	0.34	<0.01	0.48	0.03	0.48	
	3	3.16	3.00	3.05	2.94	0.07								
Milk Lactose Yield, kg/d	1	1.82	1.96	1.86	1.82	0.08								
	2	2.10	2.33	2.12	2.24	0.08	0.07	0.63	0.38	<0.01	0.04	0.89	0.62	
	3	2.31	2.52	2.33	2.46	0.08								

Milk Lactose Content, %	1	4.78	4.80	4.75	4.76	0.03	0.29	0.17	0.86	<0.01	0.09	0.67	0.46
	2	4.87	4.91	4.86	4.87	0.03							
	3	4.90	4.94	4.85	4.90	0.03							
3.5% FCM Yield ³ , kg/d	1	47.0	51.9	51.0	48.3	1.70	0.17	0.78	0.04	<0.01	0.31	0.88	0.17
	2	51.0	55.4	52.9	53.8	1.70							
	3	53.6	57.9	57.0	55.9	1.70							
ECM Yield ⁴ , kg/d	1	47.2 ^b	50.9 ^a	51.8 ^{ab}	48.1 ^{ab}	1.64	0.24	0.92	0.04	<0.01	0.40	0.89	0.12
	2	50.8	51.9	54.6	52.6	1.64							
	3	52.7	55.2	56.5	54.0	1.65							
FCM/DMI, kg/d	1	2.47	2.49	2.59	2.44	0.07	0.87	0.05	0.15	0.06	0.25	0.08	0.70
	2	2.34	2.51	2.64	2.54	0.07							
	3	2.25	2.39	2.53	2.52	0.07							
ECM/DMI, kg/d	1	2.48	2.49	2.57	2.45	0.08	0.87	0.08	0.17	0.01	0.35	0.12	0.62
	2	2.32	2.47	2.58	2.49	0.08							
	3	2.22	2.34	2.46	2.44	0.08							
Body Weight, kg	1	737	740	725	731	7.12	0.56	0.03	0.67	<0.01	0.94	0.12	0.91
	2	716	717	701	708	7.12							
	3	711	710	689	695	7.12							
BCS	1	3.31	3.33	3.25	3.28	0.04	0.82	0.03	0.56	<0.01	0.41	0.35	0.85
	2	3.22	3.22	3.15	3.18	0.04							
	3	3.19	3.14	3.07	3.08	0.04							
Insulin, μ IU	1	4.33	3.90	3.21	3.01	0.35	0.09	<0.01	0.27	0.12	0.28	0.91	0.18
	2	4.91	3.34	3.15	3.04	0.35							
	3	4.69	4.24	3.43	3.24	0.36							
Glucose, mg/dL	1	55.7	56.5	53.6	55.8	1.14	0.11	0.02	0.37	<0.01	0.77	0.31	0.88
	2	56.5	57.3	52.9	56.0	1.12							
	3	58.7	59.2	54.8	56.7	1.15							
	1	0.57	0.53	0.69	0.70	0.04	0.96	<0.01	0.95	0.04	0.91	0.92	0.25

NEFA, mmol/L	2	0.53	0.52	0.65	0.67	0.04								
	3	0.46	0.51	0.65	0.62	0.04								
BHB, mg/dL	1	10.5	8.20	10.8	9.04	1.08								
	2	9.54 ^a	7.76 ^a	12.1 ^b	10.4 ^b	1.09	0.02	0.03	0.77	0.70	0.16	<0.01	0.07	
	3	9.17 ^a	7.33 ^a	13.6 ^b	9.33 ^a	1.08								

^{a-b}Means in a row with different superscripts differ. Shown only if a three-way interaction between starch, FA, and time was observed ($P < 0.10$).

¹LS (diet containing starch at 22% DM and no supplemental FA); HS (diet containing starch at 28% DM and no supplemental FA); LS+FA (diet containing starch at 22% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1); HS+FA (diet containing starch at 28% DM and a Ca-salt containing 70% C16:0 and 20% *cis*-9 C18:1).

² P -values refer to the ANOVA results for the main effect of starch, the main effect of FA, the main effect of time, the interaction between starch and FA, the interaction between starch and time, the interaction between FA and time, and the interaction between starch, FA, and time.

³3.5% FCM = $[(0.4324 \times \text{kg of milk}) + (16.216 \times \text{kg of milk fat})]$ (NRC, 2001).

⁴ECM = $(0.327 \times \text{kg of milk}) + (12.95 \times \text{kg of milk fat}) + (7.20 \times \text{kg of milk protein})$. This equation corrects milk to a 0.68 Mcal/kg energy basis.